

ON BIGUANIDINO SULPHONES

By U. P. BASU, K. R. CHANDRAN AND ACHINTYA KAMAL SEN

Some *p*-biguanidinophenylsulphonylmethanes have been prepared and their characteristics recorded.

In the previous studies made in this laboratory (Sen Gupta and Basu, *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1949, 9, 161; Rao *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 133), it has been shown that simple sulphones containing *p*-aminophenyl substituent exhibit considerable bacteriostatic properties. Conversion of the amino group into amidino group may further alter the antibacterial spectrum (cf. Andrews *et al.*, *Lancet*, 1944, *i*, 773). Some amidino sulphones (Fuller *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 633) and some simple aromatic guanidines (King and Tonkin, *ibid.*, 1946, 1063) are again found to exhibit some antimalarial activity. Hence, it would be of interest to see the effect of introduction of biguanidino grouping in the sulphone molecule. A few of such compounds have been described in this communication.

p-Aminophenylsulphonylmethane was prepared according to the method of Sikdar and Basu (this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 343) and converted into the hydrochloride in the usual way. It was then condensed with appropriate phenyldicyandiamide to the biguanidino sulphones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenyldicyandiamides were prepared according to the method of Curd and Rose (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 726). The denitrogenation of the intermediate triazine was carried out in presence of acetone and concentrated hydrochloric acid (*ibid.*, 1946, 729).

General Method of Preparation.—*p*-Methylsulphonylaniline hydrochloride (1 mole) was refluxed with the respective dicyandiamides (1 mole) in absolute alcohol for about 10 hours. The reactants went into solution within half an hour. The reaction mixture was then cooled and diluted with requisite quantity of ether, when on scratching the hydrochlorides separated as white crystals which were recrystallised from ether-alcohol mixture (charcoal). In the case of compound (II) the hydrochloride separated within a short time after the reactants had gone in solution. After refluxing for two hours, the reaction mixture was cooled and the separated crystals were filtered off and recrystallised from water (charcoal).

The characteristics of the various compounds are listed in the following table.

TABLE I

Compound.	General appearance and melting point.	Percentage nitrogen.	
		Found.	Calc.
R. C ₆ H ₅ , HCl	White crystals, m.p. 221-22°	18.88	19.04
R. C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (p), HCl	White needles, m.p. 242-43°	18.12	17.61
R. C ₆ H ₄ Cl (p), HCl	White crystals, m.p. 205-207°	17.76	17.41
R. C ₆ H ₄ Cl (m), HCl	White prisms, m.p. 202-203°	17.60	17.41
R. C ₆ H ₄ Br (p), HCl	White crystals, m.p. 228-29°	15.48	15.63
R. C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p), HCl	White needles, m.p. 229-30°	18.22	18.35

The study of the pharmacological properties of the compounds is in progress.

BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
CALCUTTA.

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